

Topology and Symmetry in Atom Rings, Clusters and Complexes

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The degeneracies of energy eigenstates of the normal modes of vibration and of the group orbitals are generally treated within the disciplines of quantum mechanics and group theory. It is shown how such degeneracies of ring and cluster molecules of sulphur, phosphorus, selenium and tellurium as well as the ir's of the group orbitals of homoligand complexes can be dealt with topologically. That topology and symmetry in such molecules mutually help each other is also emphasised.

The study here dwells on the cooperative roles played by symmetry and topology of molecules comprising some atoms in the forms of rings and clusters and homoligands in coordination sites. The rings and clusters dealt with are S_4 , S_5 , S_6 , S_7 , S_8 , P_4 and some homocycles of Se and Te, such as Se_4^{2+} , Se_8^{2+} and Te_8^{2+} . The complexes, rings and clusters surveyed in this connection are of different symmetries such as C_{4v} , D_{4h} , D_{3d} , D_{4d} , T_d and O_h . Before describing exactly what is aimed to be done with these rings and clusters, let us acquaint ourselves with some characteristics of these molecules as have been established experimentally or calculated theoretically. Some of the exhaustive references to such works are contained in the review article by Gillespie¹, and publications by Dixon and Wasserman², Jotham³, Cotton⁴, Baird⁵ and others^{6,7}.

The experimental configurations of S_n and their theoretically established (*ab initio*)² point group symmetries are given in Fig. 1. In Table 1 are given the theoretically calculated data of *ab initio* total energies of these ring molecules², some values of their thermodynamic functions⁵, the number of vertices (N) and the corresponding Z -values ($Z = \text{half of the modular sum of the topological eigenvalues}$). Although our interest here concerns symmetry and topology, it is incidentally observed that beautiful graphical correlations exist between the above stated molecular properties and topological indices (N and Z) (Fig. 2). We shall skip interpretations of the correlations here as analogous cases for homologous series have already been discussed elsewhere^{8,9}.

It is known that symmetry helps^{10,11} in the reduction of topological graphs to obtain eigenvalues. Its extension, technique involving enforced symmetrisation¹², is also known. Scheme 1 epitomises how topology can, in its turn, predict degeneracies of molecular properties which normally lie within the provinces of symmetry and quantum mechanics.

We shall now sequentially consider three such molecular properties involving rings, clusters and homoligand complexes.

TABLE-1 NUMBER OF VERTICES, Z -VALUES, *ab initio* ENERGIES, SPECIFIC HEATS AND ENTROPIES OF SULPHUR HOMOCYCLES

Species and point group	Number of vertices (N)	Z	<i>ab initio</i> -SCF total energy (a.u.)	Specific heat (C_p) at 300 K (cal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	Entropy (S_p^\ddagger) at 300 K (cal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
$S_2 (D_{\infty h})$	2	1 0	—	—	—
$S_4 (D_{4h})^*$	4	2 0	-1 589 96	16 71	71 43
$S_5 (C_2)^*$	5	3 24	-1 987 51	21 78	84 04
$S_6 (D_{3d})$	6	4 0	-2 385 04	26 65	84 58
$S_7 (C_s)$	7	4 5	-2 782 54	31 89	99 44
$S_8 (D_{4d})$	8	4 83	-3 180 06	36 91	102 13

* Baird⁵ assumed the point groups of S_4 and S_5 as D_{2d} and C_4 respectively, whereas Dixon and Wasserman² concluded these to belong to D_{4h} and C_2

Fig. 1

Fig. 2. Plots of total energy [E_{SCF} (a.u.)] against Z (curve a) and N (curve b), C_P against N (curve c) and S_T^0 against N (curve d)

Scheme 1

Degeneracies of energy eigenstates and overlap topology :

The graph of S_6 ring molecule, as an illustration, consists of $\{V(G)\}$ – a six-vertex set each represented by a pair of sp^3 hybrids and $\{E(G)\}$ -edge set of connectivities due to overlaps of the neighbouring hybrids.

The topological matrix T comprises the elements $t_{ij} = 0$ for $i = j$ and $t_{ij} = 1$ for adjacent i and j or zero otherwise for $i \neq j$ with i and j each running over 1 to 6. The hamiltonian in the basis set of the six sp^3 hybrids is a (6×6) matrix, viz. $H = (h_{ij})$, where

$$h_{11} = \langle \phi_{sp^3}^1 | \hat{H} | \phi_{sp^3}^1 \rangle = h_{jj} \dots = \epsilon$$

and

$$h_{1j} = \langle \phi_{sp^3}^1 | \hat{H} | \phi_{sp^3}^j \rangle = a$$

for adjacent i and j ($i \neq j$) and zero otherwise. The legitimacy of the assumption of zero interaction for non-

adjacent orbitals is consistent with the nature of connectivities permitted by overlap topology. The two matrices H and T are then related as

$$H = \epsilon I + a T \tag{1}$$

where I is a (6×6) dimensional unit matrix.

It is then evident that the degeneracies of the eigenstates implicit in the H matrix are incidentally carried by the topological matrix T as well. Such interlinks between H and T ensure prediction of symmetry results, viz. the ir's (vide Table 2). The interpretation, though similar to that of planar π -systems, is here valid, in addition to planar homocycles S_4 , Se_4^{2+} , Te_4^{2+} , for the non-planar rings S_6 , S_8 , S_8^{2+} , Se_8^{2+} etc. as well.

The departures noticeable in the results of S_5 (C_2) and S_7 (C_3) systems are due to the fact that the pure topological matrices yield results characteristic of C_{5h} (hypothetical planar S_5) and C_{7h} (hypothetical planar S_7). One ought to have allowed the use of pseudo-topological parameters and possibly also the retention of perturbation elements in a suitably structured additional matrix B to enable reliable prediction of ir's. In any case, however, this would entail a number of assumed values and the interpretation would seem artificial and contrived in the final analysis.

Symmetries of the normal modes of vibrations and vibrational topology :

The ir's of the normal modes of vibrations of clusters and homocycles (P_4 , S_n , Se_n) may be anticipated from the topological degeneracies. The cluster molecule, P_4 , an oft quoted species in literature^{3,13}, is taken as an illustrative example. In keeping with our foregoing approach we have to demonstrate a relationship between the topological matrix and the vibrational hamiltonian matrix.

We consider a vibrational topology of P_4 in which the vertex set $\{V(G)\}$ of the graph are the individual displacements of the atoms at any instant and the edge set $\{E(G)\}$ are the coupling influences on the mutual displacements. The mutual coupling influences are all identical for all the P atoms, since they are all mutually equidistant and adjacent in their equilibrium configuration (Fig. 3).

TABLE 2—SULPHUR, SELENIUM AND TELLURIUM SYSTEMS

Species	Degeneracies of topological eigenvalues	Group theoretical degeneracies of the energy states	Remark
S ₂	Nondegenerate -2 Nos	Nondegenerate -2 Nos	Accord with topological result
S ₄	Nondegenerate -2 Nos Doubly degenerate -1 No	Nondegenerate -2 Nos Doubly degenerate -1 No	Accord with topological result
S ₅	Nondegenerate -1 No Doubly degenerate -2 Nos	All nondegenerate	No accord with topological result
S ₆	Nondegenerate -2 Nos Doubly degenerate -2 Nos	Nondegenerate -2 Nos Doubly degenerate -2 Nos	Accord with topological result
S ₇	Nondegenerate -1 No Doubly degenerate -3 Nos	All nondegenerate	No accord with topological result
S ₈	Nondegenerate -2 Nos Doubly degenerate -3 Nos	Nondegenerate -2 Nos Doubly degenerate -3 Nos	Accord with topological result
Se ₄ ²⁺	Results similar to S ₄		
Te ₄ ²⁺	Results similar to S ₄		
Se ₈ ²⁺	Results similar to S ₈		

P₄ molecule (T_d) has six normal modes of vibrations with normal coordinates Q_i (i = 1 to 6). The (4 × 4) topological matrix, if it be at all helpful, can at most account for the symmetry types (ir's) of four of the six normal modes. Let these four normal modes be Q₃, Q₄, Q₅ and Q₆. The (4 × 4) matrix, if desired, can be written in an augmented form as a (6 × 6) matrix with two additional rows and columns with zeros as the corresponding matrix elements. (This may be interpreted as a vibrational topological matrix of tetrahedral P₄ with inclusion of two additional ghost P atoms not participating in vibrations).

$$T^{Au} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} O^{2 \times 2} & O^{2 \times 4} \\ \hline O^{4 \times 2} & T \end{pmatrix}$$

where T^{Au} = augmented topological matrix, O^{m × n} = (m × n) dimensional null matrix and T = (4 × 4) dimensional topological matrix.

The matrix form of the vibrational hamiltonian operator in the basis set of the normal coordinates can be written, subject to satisfaction of a certain pivotal condition (vide infra), as

$$H^{vib} = \begin{pmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & Q_{13} & Q_{14} & Q_{15} & Q_{16} \\ Q_{21} & Q_{22} & Q_{23} & Q_{24} & Q_{25} & Q_{26} \\ Q_{31} & Q_{32} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ Q_{61} & Q_{62} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + Q_{ij} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & Q_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & Q_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= A + Q_{ij} T^{Au} + B \quad (2)$$

where, Q_{ij} = < Q_i | Ĥ | Q_j > and Q_{ii} = < Q_i | Ĥ | Q_i >

Assuming that the normal coordinates Q₁, Q₂ have symmetries different from those of Q₃, Q₄, Q₅ and Q₆, the matrix elements Q₁₃, Q₁₄...Q₁₆, Q₂₃ Q₂₄...Q₂₆ and their transposed counterparts are all zeros in the A matrix. Hence H^{vib} is essentially block diagonal in form.

The pivotal condition referred to above is that the off-diagonal matrix elements Q_{ij}'s, representing coupling interactions, are the same or nearly so for all i's and j's (i ≠ j) in those integrals (i, j = 3 to 6) where symmetries of the normal modes permit the survival of < Q_i | Ĥ | Q_j >. Assuming that all such integrals survive, the relation (equation 2) is a valid one. The apparent conflict that arises due to disappearance of some of the Q_{ij}'s for symmetry reasons and thus impairing the structure of the second matrix (and hence eqn. 2 as well) will be sorted out shortly.

Since equation 2 holds for the block-diagonal H^{vib} matrix, it can be shown that

$$\text{Eigenvalues of } H^{vib} = \text{Eigenvalues of } A + \text{Eigenvalues of } T^{Au} + \text{Eigenvalues of } B$$

Each eigenvalue of H^{vib} is the sum of three corresponding component eigenvalues coming from A, Q_{ij}, T^{Au} and B, one apiece. Since the eigenvalues contributions from the A matrix to vibrations along the normal coordinates Q₃, Q₄, Q₅ and Q₆ are all zeros, any type of degeneracy or non-degeneracy among the normal modes with these normal coordinates must simultaneously be dormant in and sustained by the B and T^{Au} matrices only. Therefore, the nature of T^{Au} alone, and hence of T (topological matrix), will indicate via its eigenvalues, the degeneracies of vibrational energies and consequently the degeneracies of the normal coordinates Q₃, Q₄, Q₅ and Q₆ and thus specify their broad symmetry types.

To revert to the apparent difficulty, as indicated earlier, caused by the disappearances of some of the Q_{ij}'s, thus invalidating equation 2, it may be mentioned that such disappearances would make Q_{ij} T^{Au} matrix (hence T' matrix) of the vibrational hamiltonian block diagonal. Since in the

TABLE 3—DEGENERACIES OF TOPOLOGICAL EIGENVALUES AND SYMMETRY TYPES OF NORMAL MODES OF VIBRATIONS IN RINGS AND CLUSTER MOLECULES

Species and point groups	Locations of the atoms	Total no of normal modes of vibrations	Degeneracies of topological eigenvalues*	Broad symmetry types (ir's) (from topology)	Total set of ir's of normal modes (from Group Theory)	No of normal modes, symmetry types of which are revealed by topology
$P_4 (T_d)$	Atoms at the vertices	6	(a) Nd-one (b) D(3)-one	(a) A or B (b) T	$A_1 E$ T_2	4 out of 6
$S_2 (D_{\infty h})$	On C_{∞} axis	1	Nd-one	Σ_g^+ or Σ_g^- or Σ_u^+ or Σ_u^-	Σ_g^+	1 out of 1
$S_4 (D_{4h})$	At the four vertices of a square	6	(a) Nd-two (b) D(2)-one	(a) A and B or $2A$'s or $2B$'s (b) E	(a) $A_{1g}, B_{1g},$ B_{2u}, B_{2g} (b) E_u	4 out of 6
$S_5 (C_2)$	One on C_2 axis, the remaining four distributed on two general planes	9	(a) Nd-one (b) D(2)-two	No correct conclusion can be drawn	—	—
$S_6 (D_{3d})$	At the vertices of the chair form (cyclohexane type)	12	(a) Nd-two (b) D(2)-two	(a) A and B , or $2A$'s or $2B$'s (b) $2E$'s	$2A_{1g}, A_{1u}, A_{2u}$ $2E_g, 2E_u$	6 out of 12
$S_7 (C_s)$	One on the σ plane, others are at general points	15	(a) Nd-one (b) D(2)-three	No correct conclusion can be drawn	—	—
$S_8 (D_{4d})$	At the vertices of two squares in staggered orientation	18	(a) Nd-two (b) D(2)-three	(a) (A and B), or $2A$'s or $2B$'s (b) $3E$'s	$2A_1, B_1, B_2$ $2E_1, 3E_2, 2E_3$	8 out of 18

*Nd = nondegenerate, D(2) = doubly degenerate, D(3) = triply degenerate

most general relation (equation 2), the topological matrix T occurs in the hamiltonian, the special case of the occurrence of block diagonal T' matrix in the hamiltonian indicates the amenability to reduction into T' form of the original non-block diagonal topological T matrix through a suitable similarity transformation. The degeneracies of the eigenvalues of the topological T matrix will, therefore, still speak for the degeneracies of the $Q_{ij} T'$ matrix.

Actual solutions indicate the following eigenvalues for the T matrix of P_4 : $\epsilon_1 = 3$, $\epsilon_2 = -1$, $\epsilon_3 = -1$ and $\epsilon_4 = -1$. Hence the vibrational topology of P_4 predicts a one-dimensional IR (A or B) for one mode and a three-dimensional ir, T , for the three other modes. A complete symmetry treatment of P_4 leads to A_1 and T_2 ir's for the four normal modes and an $E - ir$ for the two other degenerate modes, that two remaining outside the pale of the present topological treatment.

The treatment meted out to P_4 can simultaneously be extended to sulphur rings $S_4 (D_{4h})$, $S_5 (C_2)$, $S_6 (D_{3d})$, $S_7 (C_s)$ and $S_8 (D_{4d})$. As in the former instance, this treatment involves the proviso that the magnitudes of the off-diagonal coupling-interaction matrix elements of any two adjacent atoms are the same. The results are given in Table 3. It will be noted that except for S_5 and S_7 , correct topological

predictions for the broad symmetry types (ir's) of the normal modes of vibrations of rings and clusters can be made and these are in conformity with the group theoretical results. Of course the details of symmetry types (such as 1, 2 subscripts, g, u , subscripts or prime (')) double primes ('') superscripts) can not be ascertained from topology.

Ir's of group orbitals and topological degeneracies :

To understand the nature of the symmetries involved in the group orbitals of a homoligand complex (say of O_h, T_d, D_{4h}, C_{4v} symmetries) we need to consider a graph wherein the vertex set $\{V(G)\}$ comprises the ligands (metal-ion excluded) and the edge set $\{E(G)\}$ consists of interligand interactions between adjacent ligands. The ligands are thus connected through interligand interactions in the topological graph although such interligand chemical bonds do not occur in a classical picture of the metal ion complex. As an illustration the topological graph of the complex $[CoF_6]^{3-}$ is considered. The numbers 1 to 6 represent vertices and the edges (interligand interactions) connect the equidistant vertices (Fig. 4). The six fluorine atoms contribute six atomic orbitals, ϕ_i 's, one apiece, for coordination.

If H represents the electronic hamiltonian of the total complex ion, then

Fig 4

$$H = H_1 + H_2 + H_3 + H_4$$

where,

$$(i) H_1 = \sum_p H^{\text{core}}(p), \text{ where } H^{\text{core}}(p) = -(\hbar^2/2m) \nabla_p^2 -$$

$$\sum_A Z_A e^2/r_{AP}$$

summation over p covers all electrons, summation over A includes all nuclei.

$$(ii) H_2 = \sum_{m < n} \sum e^2/r_{mn}$$

m, n represent metal-ion electrons only, summation is over metal-ion electrons.

$$(iii) H_3 = \sum_m \sum_k e^2/r_{mk}$$

m = metal-ion electron, k = ligand electron. This represents metal electron-ligand-electron repulsion interaction.

$$(iv) H_4 = \sum_{k < l} \sum e^2/r_{kl}$$

k, l are ligand electrons. This term represents ligand electron-ligand electron interaction

H_3 can be approximated by a central field repulsion term, since the electrons on the metal form a sort of an inner negatively charged sphere acting on the ligand electrons at an average distance \bar{r} , i.e.

$$H_3 \approx H_3' = \sum_l Z' e^2/\bar{r}$$

where summation covers all ligand electrons; $-Z'e$ is the effective charge of the negatively charged sphere due to metal ion electrons only. Therefore

$$H = H_1 + H_2 + H_3' + H_4$$

$$\text{where, } H_4 = \sum_{k < l} \sum e^2/r_{kl}$$

may be interpreted as the ligand-ligand interaction hamiltonian Using this total hamiltonian it is not possible to segregate and show clearly the effect of interligand interaction on symmetry. As an alternative, a very gross approximation is to be made much like in the manner of *crystal field theory* wherein the ligand electrons are assumed to be present without their nuclei. To find an approximate effect of interligand interaction, it may be supposed that the ligand electrons are present in an overall approximate central field besides their own mutual repulsive field, i.e.

$$H_{\text{app}} = H_{\text{cent}} + \sum_{k < l} \sum e^2/r_{kl} = (H_1' + H_2' + H_3' + H_4) + H_4$$

$$\text{where, } H_1' = \sum_p H^{\text{core}}(p') = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \sum_p \nabla_p^2 - \sum_p Z e^2/r_p$$

(Difference from H_1 is that summation over nuclei is absent here)

H_2' is an assumed approximate central field part substituting for H_2 , and H_3' and H_4 are what have already been described. Taking H_4 as the perturbation Hamiltonian and expressing it in the matrix form, H^{lig} in the basis set of ϕ_i 's (the ligand orbitals meant for coordination) we have

$$H^{\text{lig}} = \begin{pmatrix} h_{11} & h_{12} & h_{13} & \dots & h_{16} \\ h_{21} & h_{22} & h_{23} & \dots & h_{26} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ h_{61} & h_{62} & h_{63} & \dots & h_{66} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} h_{11} & & & & & \\ & h_{22} & & & & \\ & & \cdot & & & \\ & & & \cdot & & \\ & & & & \cdot & \\ & & & & & h_{66} \end{pmatrix} + \xi \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= \alpha I + \zeta T$$

where, $h_{11} = \langle \phi_1 | H_4 | \phi_1 \rangle = \langle \phi_j | H_4 | \phi_j \rangle = \dots = \alpha$

$h_{ij} = \langle \phi_i | H_4 | \phi_j \rangle = \dots = h_{kl} = \zeta$ for adjacent i and j, k and l ,

I = unit matrix,

T = topological matrix of the interligand interaction graph.

Diagonalisation of H^{lig} will lead to simultaneous diagonalisation of the T matrix indicating the type of degeneracies of the six group orbitals. Incidentally this will also specify the nature of degeneracies of six or more of the molecular orbitals out of the full set of MO's of the complex, provided some of the metal ion d -atomic orbitals have symmetries in common with those of the aforesaid group orbitals. Table 4 contains the list of broad symmetry types of group orbitals predicted by topology for homoligand complexes of different point group symmetries. These are compiled on the basis that each ligand contributes one atomic orbital for bonding.

Ligands contributing a number of atomic orbitals each for bonding with metal ions can also be treated topologically^{14,15}. However, using the procedure we have followed here, it can be shown that even when each ligand contributes a number of orbitals for coordination, the broad symmetry types will still be the same as for a single orbital, but the number of each individual broad type will increase

TABLE 4—BROAD SYMMETRY TYPES OF LIGAND GROUP ORBITALS AS INFERRED FROM TOPOLOGY (EACH LIGAND CONTRIBUTES ONE ORBITAL FOR COORDINATION)

Point group of the homoligand complex	Degeneracies of topological eigenvalues and their number*	Symmetry types inferred from column 2 (i.e. from topology)	Actual symmetry types inferred from Group Theory
T_d	(a) Nd-one (b) D(3)-one	(a) A or B (b) T	(a) A_1 (b) T_2
O_h (octahedral)	(a) Nd-one (b) D(2)-one (c) D(3)-one	(a) A or B (b) E (c) T	(a) A_{1g} (b) E_g (c) T_{1u}
D_{4h} (square-planar)	(a) Nd-two (b) D(2)-one	(a) (A and B) or $2A'$'s or $2B'$'s (b) E	(a) A_{1g} and B_{1g} or other possibilities depending on the basic symmetries of the ligand orbitals (b) E_u
C_{4v} square-pyramid, ligands at the vertices of the basal plane	(a) Nd-two (b) D(2)-one	(a) (A and B); or $2A'$'s or $2B'$'s (b) E	(a) A_1 and B_1 (b) E

*Nd = nondegenerate, D(2) = doubly degenerate, D(3) = triply degenerate.

as far as topology is concerned. However, the finer details of symmetry from group theoretical viewpoint will exhibit the internal distinctions within a given broad symmetry type, say B_{1g} and B_{2u} within the type B , found in larger number by topology.

We need to consider finally the limitations and difficulties attending the application of the topological process for prediction of degeneracies. In so doing one has to take care of both the hamiltonian and the point group of the molecule.

(i) The Hamiltonian matrix should commute with the topological matrix. If not, one may recast the Hamiltonian, shedding its such minor parts as will not tell upon the desired property (here degeneracy) and test its commutivity (vide the instance of homoligand complex). If it still fails, the present process becomes inadmissible.

(ii) For homo-atom ring-type molecules, whether planar or nonplanar, commutivity is ensured, but the topological degeneracies are characteristic of the corresponding planar D_{nh} symmetry irrespective of the actual symmetry of the nonplanar molecules, e.g. S_6 (D_{3d}), S_8 (D_{4d}), S_5 (C_2), S_7 (C_3). A minor reduction in symmetry, such as from D_{6h} to D_{3d} of S_6 , conserves the broad symmetry type of the degeneracy. In other words, A , B , E of D_{6h} remain unchanged on reduction of symmetry to D_{3d} . But in a major shift of symmetry, such as from D_{5h} to C_2 of S_5 , conservation of degeneracy is lost rendering the process inapplicable (vide Tables 2 and 3). However, for homo-atom or homo-ligand cluster molecules, the topological results, unlike the ring-types, are characteristic of the corresponding

molecular symmetries. If, therefore, the Hamiltonian commutivity is ensured, the topology-based prediction becomes valid.

(iii) The ring or non-ring type molecules containing one heteroatom in the conglomerate of homo-atoms, e.g. core part of pyridine (C_5N) (ring type-symmetry C_{2v}) or trivenylammonia $[(CH_2 = CH)]_3 \equiv N$, core part (C_6N)-symmetry C_{3v}) may be regarded as topological perturbations of benzene (core part C_6 -symmetry D_{6h}) and trivinylmethyl radical $[(CH_2 = CH)]_3 \equiv C$; core part (C_7)-symmetry D_{3h}] respectively, where one N atom is substituted by a C atom acting as a pseudo-nitrogen atom in the molecular graphs. Although the topological matrices of the pseudo-graphs (C_6) and (C_7) will commute with the respective Hamiltonians of the original molecules, the major shift in symmetry in the former case (from D_{6h} to C_{2v}) renders the topology-based approach invalid. But topology predicts correctly for the latter heteroatom containing molecule. In general, the present approach is rendered invalid for most of the heteroatom containing molecules because of severe mauling of symmetry.

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